

MICROBIOLOGICAL INDICATORS OF FINISHED PRODUCTS OF RABBIT MEAT

¹I.D. Ataxodjayeva, ²R.R. Akramova^{1,2}Tashkent Institute of chemical technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.¹e-mail: inoyatatakhodjaeva@gmail.com<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8362023>

Abstract. The popularity of rabbit meat is primarily associated with a global trend: grows interest in healthy eating. Rabbit meat, as a diet, meets the new healthy life.

Environmental problems, which often turn into allergies in babies, determined the demand for dietary nutrition using rabbit meat. For proper nutrition, necessary to know, that the importance of individual nutrients for people and clearly imagine the need for them depending on age, profession, climate and social conditions. As is known, since every living cell, every tissue of the body consists mainly of protein.

Rabbit meat is able to reduce the dose of received radiation in the human body, helps postoperative patients. Due to its low fat and cholesterol content, given the high biological value, tenderness of rabbit meat, nutritionists recommend using rabbit meat in their diet for various diseases of the gastrointestinal tract, stomach, biliary tract, liver, allergies, hypertension and others. Meat is easily digested by gastric juices and more fully digestible by the human body. It is also useful for people of extreme professions: pilots, divers, athletes, workers in hazardous industries, residents of contaminated areas. Rabbit meat is recommended for children, it is included in baby food for the smallest.

Keywords: dietary and diabetic nutrition, rabbit meat, product for the middle class.

Аннотация. Популярность крольчатины в первую очередь связана с мировым трендом: растет интерес к здоровому питанию. Мясо кролика, как диетическое, отвечает новой здоровой жизни.

Экологические проблемы, часто переходящие в аллергию у малышей, определили востребованность диетического питания с использованием крольчатины. Для правильного питания необходимо знать, что значение отдельных питательных веществ для человека и четко представлять потребность в них в зависимости от возраста, профессии, климатических и социальных условий. Как известно, поскольку каждая живая клетка, каждая ткань организма состоит в основном из белка.

Мясо кролика способно снизить дозу полученной радиации в организме человека, помогает послеоперационным больным. Благодаря низкому содержанию жира и холестерина, учитывая высокую биологическую ценность, нежность крольчатины, диетологи рекомендуют использовать крольчатину в своем рационе при различных заболеваниях желудочно-кишечного тракта, желудка, желчевыводящих путей, печени, аллергии, гипертонической болезни и других. Мясо легко переваривается желудочным соком и более полно усваивается организмом человека. Полезен он и людям экстремальных профессий: летчикам, водолазам, спортсменам, работникам вредных производств, жителям загрязненных территорий. Мясо кролика рекомендуется детям, его включают в детское питание для самых маленьких.

Ключевые слова: диетическое и диабетическое питание, мясо кролика, продукты для среднего класса

Annotatsiya. Quyon go'shtining mashhurligi birinchi navbatda global tendentsiya bilan bog'liq; sog'lom ovqatlanishga qiziqish ortib bormoqda. Quyon go'shti, parhez sifatida, yangi

sog'lom hayotga javob beradi. Atrof-muhit muammolari, ko'pincha chaqaloqlarda allergiyaga aylanib, quyon go'shti yordamida parhez ovqatlanishiga bo'lgan talabni aniqladi. To'g'ri ovqatlanish uchun inson uchun individual ozuqa moddalarining ahamiyatini bilish va ularning yoshi, kasbi, iqlim va ijtimoiy sharoitlariga qarab zarurligini aniq tushunish kerak. Ma'lumki, har bir tirik hujayra, tananing har bir to'qimasi asosan oqsildan iborat. Quyon go'shti inson tanasida olingan nurlanish dozasini kamaytirishi va operatsiyadan keyingi bemorlarga yordam berishi mumkin. Yog 'va xolesterin miqdori past bo'lganligi sababli, quyon go'shtining yuqori biologik qiymatini, nozikligini hisobga olgan holda, dietologlar oshqozon-ichak trakti, oshqozon, o't yo'llari, jigar, allergiya, gipertenziya va boshqalarning turli kasalliklari uchun o'z dietasida quyon go'shtidan foydalanishni tavsiya etadilar. Go'sht me'da shirasi tomonidan oson hazm qilinadi va inson tanasi tomonidan to'liqroq so'riladi. Bu ekstremal kasb egalari uchun ham foydalidir: uchuvchilar, g'avvoslar, sportchilar, xavfli sanoat ishchilari, ifloslangan hududlar aholisi. Quyon go'shti bolalar uchun tavsiya etiladi, u go'daklik davridagi bolalar taomnomasiga kiritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: parhez va qandli diabet ovqatlanish, quyon go'shti, aholi uchun oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari.

The State program for the development of agriculture and regulation of agricultural products, raw materials and food markets, strategies for improving the quality of food products in Uzbekistan 2030. Taking into account the existing backlogs in the production of meat of some animal species, precocious animals and birds are of significant interest to Uzbekistan, the production of meat of which can be increased at the expense of internal reserves.

One of the promising industries in this regard is rabbit breeding. In order to develop this industry and increase production in the domestic market, a program is being implemented in Uzbekistan:

- Development and increase of rabbit breeding production on the territory of Uzbekistan;
- The development of rabbit breeding is objectively determined by high economic efficiency, which in turn is due to the high fertility and precocity of rabbits, as well as the balance of chemical composition and high biological value.

Today in the world, from 1.0 to 1.7 million tons of rabbit meat are produced in different countries. According to estimates, in the 90s, about 3 million tons of rabbit meat were produced in the world every year, while the zoning of the industry is traced. This is due to the economy, culture, national cuisine of different countries of the world and traditions in the nutrition of peoples.

At the moment, for the development of rabbit breeding, it is necessary to create an infrastructure that includes the production of feed, the construction of new slaughter and processing shops, the creation of a system sales of products. In economically developed regions of the world, large -scale production prevails, where 55% of the total volume of rabbit meat is produced. The remaining 45% is occupied by small traditional farms.

The undisputed leader in the production of rabbit meat is China, where for in 2017, about 735 thousand tons were produced, while the level of rabbit meat consumption in this country is low. This is due to the fact that rabbit meat is mainly exported on a global scale.

In the rhythm of modern life, the ease and speed of cooking rabbit meat is important for people, the cost is important for someone, and most importantly, information about the safety and usefulness of products. In order to expand the range and promote the market steadily,

manufacturers prefer to pack parts of the carcass, rather than sell it as a whole. With an increase in production costs, and therefore with an increase in prices, buyers are willing to pay for 15-20% more for a rabbit meat product in modern packaging that provides good consumer properties. Have become popular as well products in pickled form and ready to eat. In the future, it is planned to increase the number and volume of production of industrial enterprises, the development of high-quality genetic centers created on the basis of already operating industrial farms or built by foreign companies to meet the growing demand in the Uzbek market to quickly fill the existing shortage of meat products. Five years ago, rabbit meat was difficult to find on store shelves, it was presented only in the private sector. In Uzbekistan, not there were industrial enterprises for its production.

To increase the demand for rabbit meat, it is necessary to more actively form new knowledge about the benefits of rabbit products, the possibilities of rational and purposeful use for various social strata and physiological groups of the population, taking into account professional affiliation.

Therefore, we do canned products as a pate and stew in our laboratory condition.

Pate a shell of mostly cylindrical dough for spicy stew, a dish of minced meat, baked in a shell of dough or served in a terrine - an exquisite snack dish in the form of a viscous homogeneous pasty mass of boiled or fried and then pureed meat.

Stewed meat (stew) is a canned meat product obtained from sterilized meat cooked in its own juice. Stew as a product is completely ready for independent use, it can be part of other dishes.

We checked the microbiological and safety indicators of finished products.

Comparative composition of meat of farm animals

Table 1

Name of materials	Mass fraction of grams per 100 g of product				Ratio Fat:protein
	Protein	Fat	Moisture	Ash	
Rabbit meat	20,2	10,6	69,0	1,2	0,3
Beef	17,0	14,0	67,0	2,0	0,8
Chicken meat - broilers	19,7	13,8	65,4	1,1	0,7

We carried out a microbiological check on the following table

No	Types of products	Time	Temperature	Moisture(%)	Results of microbiological indicators
1	Pate	72 hours	36	100	Not found
2	Stew	72 hours	36	100	Not found

On the following photos obtaining microbiologic results after canning processes.

Pate 1

Pate 2

Stew 1

Stew 2

Therefore, microbiological indicators are the main criteria for safety of products, in addition chemical and physical including, microbiological indicators shows damage or freshness of raw materials and finished products after the technological processes.

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